

THE ACTION OF HYDROGEN SULPHIDE ON PERMANGANATES PART I. CALCIUM AND SILVER PERMANGANATES.

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Action of hydrogen sulphide on 1% solution of calcium and 0.5% solution of silver permanganates has been studied.

Dunncliff and Nijhawan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1) have found that the action of hydrogen sulphide on a neutral solution of potassium permanganate yields hydrated manganese dioxide, sulphur, potassium sulphate and potassium dithionate. Excess of hydrogen sulphide converts manganese dioxide into manganese sulphide and decomposes potassium dithionate into potassium sulphate, thiosulphate and sulphur. The present work communicates the action of hydrogen sulphide on calcium and silver permanganates.

When a slow current of hydrogen sulphide is passed through 1% solution of calcium permanganate of tested purity, the purple solution deposits a dark brown precipitate. After a short time the solution becomes colourless and the precipitate still remains dark brown. Further passage of hydrogen sulphide results in the conversion of this precipitate into a sand-like precipitate of greyish colour. Finally the precipitate becomes pink due to the formation of manganous sulphide and the solution is found to be of yellow colour due to the formation of polysulphides. After passing the gas for several hours, even the polysulphides decompose giving a colourless solution. In order to determine the mechanism of the reaction, it was investigated at different stages.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Products of Reaction when Hydrogen Sulphide Water is added until the purple colour of the Calcium Permanganate just disappears.

To a calcium permanganate solution (1%, 100 c. c.) hydrogen sulphide water was added from a burette, until the purple colour of the permanganate just disappeared. The solution, containing the black precipitate, was filtered through a sintered glass crucible. The solution gave tests for sulphate and calcium readily. Thiosulphate was found to be present in traces. The formation of thiosulphate could be obviated if hydrogen sulphide water was added exactly to the decolorisation stage. Tri-, tetra-, and penta-thionates were found to be absent. The presence of dithionate was suspected since solutions gave small quantities of

sulphur dioxide on treatment with strong hydrochloric acid, which could be estimated by absorbing it in a standard solution of iodine.

Analysis of the Filtrate.—Calcium was estimated volumetrically after precipitating it as calcium oxalate. Sulphate was estimated gravimetrically. It was found that the amount of calcium recovered was less than that required for the formation of calcium sulphate. A portion of the filtrate was treated with potassium bromate and hydrochloric acid to oxidise any calcium dithionate, present. The free $(\text{SO}_4)^{2-}$ was precipitated as barium sulphate in cold (Mitchel, "Modern Methods of Chemical Analysis", p. 136). In the solution which was neutral, calcium was quantitatively accounted for as sulphate and dithionate (Ca in the precipitate : 40.33% and in the filtrate : 59.67%). Ca in the filtrate was accounted for as SO_4^{2-} , 93.3% ; $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, 6.7%.

The above experiments showed that only part of the calcium came in the filtrate as calcium sulphate and calcium dithionate.

The amount of calcium remained constant in the precipitate even if an experiment was repeated several times under identical conditions. In order to find out the way in which calcium is combined with the oxides of manganese, the precipitate was first treated with dilute solution of potassium hydroxide to remove co-ordinated sulphur compounds, if any (*cf.* Dunncliff and Kotwani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 3214). The alkali extract did not contain any calcium or manganese. The precipitate was then treated with strong hydrochloric acid and the chlorine evolved was absorbed in U-tubes containing concentrated solution of potassium iodide. The liquid left over from this estimation was made slightly alkaline. The total manganese in it was removed as manganese sulphide and was estimated by the pyrophosphate method. Calcium present in the filtrate after the removal of Mn was estimated volumetrically after precipitating it as calcium oxalate. Estimation gave values of 7.2 : 1 for the molecular ratio of MnO : MnO_2 and 1.4 : 7.2 : 1 for the molecular ratio of CaO : MnO : MnO_2 (*vide* Table I, Expt. No. 3).

In order to elucidate the composition of the dark brown precipitate of the intermediate stage, the composition of the dark brown precipitate formed in the preliminary stages was also determined. In the first experiment (Table I, Expt. No. 1) the amount of hydrogen sulphide water added was one quarter of the hydrogen sulphide water, which was used for the intermediate stage. The estimation gave values of 1.6 : 1 : 3.66 for the molecular ratio of CaO : MnO : MnO_2 . The ratio almost corresponds exactly to the ratio of the formula of the complex $2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{MnO} \cdot 3\text{MnO}_2$ (*vide* Table II). In the intermediate stages the

molecular ratio corresponds to the ratio of the formula of the complex compound $2\text{CaO}\cdot 9\text{MnO}\cdot \text{MnO}_2$. Complex compounds of potassium of similar structures have also been obtained by reducing potassium permanganate with hydrogen peroxide, sulphur dioxide, etc., and of some other metals by different methods (*cf.* Mellor, "Treatise in Inorganic Chemistry," Vol. XII, p. 274). By analogy the compound obtained in the intermediate stage would be called calcium manganous manganite and the compound obtained in the preliminary stage would be called calcium manganous trimanganite. (The authors have also detected the presence of similar compounds in the elementary stages in the reduction of potassium and ammonium permanganates by hydrogen sulphide. The work is under investigation).

More experiments were performed to investigate the formation of other complex compounds between the preliminary and the intermediate stages. Half the amount of hydrogen sulphide water that was required for the intermediate stage was added. The results are given in Table I, Expt. No. 2. The estimations give values of 1:1.56: 2.5 for the molecular ratio of $\text{CaO} : \text{MnO} : \text{MnO}_2$. From calculation it appears to be a mixture of the complex compounds formed in the preliminary and intermediate stages. The composition of the various complexes are given in Table II. The experiments were performed in duplicate.

In the preliminary stages precipitation of sulphur was not noticed due to an excess of the oxidising agent present. In the present case sulphylic acid $\text{S}(\text{OH})_2$ may be considered as the precursor of sulphur acids formed in the reaction.

If the precipitate is allowed to remain in contact with dilute solution of potassium hydroxide for some hours, the alkali extract gives tests for sulphur acids, but calcium and manganese are found to be absent. This may be due to the presence of co-ordinated sulphur acids (Dunnicliff and Kotwani, *loc. cit.*) or probably it may be due to the oxidation of the adsorbed hydrogen sulphide in the presence of an alkali. This point is under investigation.

After the intermediate stage, further addition of hydrogen sulphide water makes the solution alkaline and results in thiosulphate formation.

Analysis of the Products formed when Hydrogen Sulphide gas is passed through Calcium Permanganate Solution to produce Manganese Sulphide and Polysulphides.

Hydrogen sulphide was passed through calcium permanganate solution for one hour; the brown precipitate totally changed into manganese sulphide

and the filtrate became yellow due to the formation of polysulphides. Sodium bicarbonate was added and a stream of carbon dioxide was passed through the filtrate to remove excess of hydrogen sulphide and to decompose the polysulphides formed (*cf.* Bagster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2631). The solution obtained after filtration was made up to a known volume and was analysed for calcium and sulphur acids.

From Table II it appears that the value of $(\text{SO}_4)^n$ obtained after bromination is accounted for as $(\text{SO}_4)^n$ and $(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^n$ present in the filtrate, thus showing the absence of the dithionate in the polysulphide and in the final stages, due probably to the hydrolysis of the dithionate to thiosulphate and sulphate (*cf.* Dunncliff and Nijhawan, *loc. cit.*). The thiosulphate formation is thus favoured by the increased reactivity of alkaline hydrolysis.

Expt. No. 3 (Table II) indicates the various products formed when hydrogen sulphide is passed into calcium permanganate solution for ten hours. The filtrate obtained is colourless. It is found that the values of sulphate and thiosulphate have still increased. The $(\text{SO}_4)^n$ after bromination is again accounted for by $(\text{SO}_4)^n$ and $(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^n$. It is interesting to note that the values of calcium in the final stage are almost wholly accounted for as $(\text{SO}_4)^n$ and $(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^n$ present in the filtrate, and these values approximate to 5 molecules of calcium sulphate to 1 molecule of calcium thiosulphate. The results of the experiments of the last stage can be expressed by the equation,

Calculating from the experimental values the percentages of CaSO_4 (39.44%), CaS_2O_3 (8.7%) and MnS (62.6%), the molecular ratio comes to be 5:1:12.2.

The Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Silver Permanganate.—On passing a slow current of pure hydrogen sulphide through a solution of silver permanganate (about 0.5%), a dark brown precipitate began to separate and the purple colour of the permanganate was discharged slowly. After the disappearance of the purple colour and the formation of dark brown precipitate, no further change was noticed in the reaction mixture.

The precipitate, obtained by passing an excess of hydrogen sulphide, contained sulphur and sulphides of silver and manganese. In the filtrate manganese was totally accounted for as sulphate. Found (Mn, 0.152 g. calc. from $(\text{SO}_4)^n$: Mn, 0.151 g.).

Analysis of the Products formed when Hydrogen Sulphide Water is added just to remove the purple Colour of the Permanganate.

The filtrate obtained after the addition of hydrogen sulphide water gave

TABLE I.
Products of the precipitate at various stages of decomposition of calcium permanganate solution (1%).

No.	H ₂ S aq.	Ca (MnO ₄) ₂	CaO.	MnO ₂ .	MnO ₂ .	Decomp. Ca (MnO ₄) ₂ .	Compound proposed.	Ratio CaO : MnO : MnO ₂ Calc.
1.	20 c.c.	100	0.0555 g.	0.0425 g.	0.1480 g.	33.2%	2CaO. 9MnO ₂ . 3MnO ₂	1.6 : 1 : 3.66
2.	40	100	0.0668 ¹	0.0919	0.1650	57.75	Probably a mixture of the two compounds.	1.8 : 1 : 3.67
3.	80	100	0.0848	0.4600	0.0601	*100	2CaO. 9MnO ₂ . MnO ₂ ²	1.4 : 7.2 : 1

* 100% decomposition indicates stage at which the purple colour of the permanganate just disappeared.

TABLE II.

The polysulphide and the final stage.
Ca(MnO₄)₂ = 50 c.c. containing 0.4817 g. per 50 c.c. water.

No.	H ₂ S gas bubbled.	Mn ²⁺ .	Ca.	*[SO ₄] ²⁻ cold.	(SO ₄) ²⁻ .	(SO ₄) ²⁻ after bromination.	(SO ₄) ²⁻ in terms of (SO ₄) ²⁻ .	Total (SO ₄) ²⁻ due to SO ₄ ²⁻ and free (SO ₄) ²⁻ .
1.	1 hour	0.1906 g.	0.069 g.	0.1205 g.	0.0196 g.	0.1531 g.	0.0336 g.	0.1867 g.
2.	1	0.1906	0.069	0.1203	0.0196	0.1533	0.0336	0.1869
3.	10	0.1906	0.069	0.1341	0.0308	0.1868	0.0538	0.2406

¹(Mean value).

TABLE III.

Silver permanganate used = 6.5095 g. per litre.

No.	AgMnO ₄ used.	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
1.	400 c.c.	0.4653 g.	(SO ₄) ²⁻ pptd. (cold).	(SO ₄) ²⁻ , after bromination.	Mn.	Ag.	(SO ₄) ²⁻ corresponding to Mn.	Diff. bet. Cols. II and III, i.e. (SO ₄) ²⁻ in terms of (S ₂ O ₈) ²⁻	Silver corresponding to Ag-dithionate from Col. VII.	(SO ₄) ²⁻ corresponding to Ag from Col. V.	The sum of the values from Col. VI, VII and IX.
2.	400	0.4681	0.4850	0.4875	0.1930	0.3100	0.3368	0.0184	0.0205	0.1287	0.4890

tests for silver, manganese and sulphate. Thiosulphate was not detected, though the solution evolved a small amount of sulphur dioxide with hydrochloric acid. The solution remained neutral at this stage and also after further addition of hydrogen sulphide water. Complete quantitative analysis of the solution showed that silver (estimated as AgCl) was accounted for as (SO₄)²⁻ and (S₂O₈)²⁻, while Mn (estimated as Mn₂P₂O₇, after the removal of silver) as sulphate only. The results are embodied in Table III.

To elucidate the composition of the products formed in the precipitate, different amounts of hydrogen sulphide water were added and the precipitates obtained were analysed for the oxides of silver and manganese. Table IV embodies the results of the various experiments. 100% Decomposition of the silver permanganate indicates the stage at which the purple colour of the permanganate just disappeared by the slow addition of hydrogen sulphide water. The reaction was not complete at this stage. The presence of silver sulphide and manganese sulphide in traces did not permit determination of the exact composition of the precipitate at this stage.

TABLE IV.

AgMnO_4 decomposed	Ag_2O .	MnO .	MnO_2 .	AgMnO_4 decomposed.	Ag_2O .	MnO .	MnO_2 .
29.42%	0.0333 g.	0.0264 g.	0.0357 g.	51.49	0.0574 g.	0.0049 g.	0.0588 g.
33.76	0.0450	0.0207	0.0443	72.65	0.0888	0.0218	0.0718
35.1	0.0233	0.0224	0.0435	100.00	0.2107	0.1149	0.0008

Table IV shows that there is a gradual change in the beginning in the amounts of the products formed. When the decomposition is about 35% (just like the decomposition of calcium permanganate) there is a sudden change in the amounts of the products formed and the decomposition of the precipitate corresponds to the formula $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot 3\text{MnO} \cdot 5\text{MnO}_2$. The formation of the products after this stage becomes irregular until the compound is changed into silver and manganese sulphides.

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